

Measuring the Impact of Cultural Innovation, Marketing Innovation, and Product Innovation on the Firm's Performance of Small-Medium Enterprises. A Study of Textile Industry in Multan Region

Irfan Ahmad Khan, Amir Hussain Shar, Mumtaz Ali Junejo

Article Info

Article History

Received:
March 02, 2022

Accepted:
October 04, 2022

Keywords :

Cultural Innovation,
Marketing Innovation,
Product Innovation,
Firm's Performance,
Small Medium
Enterprises

Abstract

This research is applied in terms of objective and descriptive-co relational in terms of method. The research population included Multan region's Small and Medium Enterprise employees in industrial city of Multan, Pakistan. The sample size was determined to be 291 employees and owners of Small-Medium Enterprises. A standard questionnaire and personally visit and field methods were used to collect data. Structural equation modeling and Smart SPSS software were used to analyze the data. The research results suggest that innovation culture has a significant effect on firm's performance of Small-Medium Enterprises, Marketing innovation has a significant effect on firm's performance of Small-Medium Enterprises, and Product Innovation has a significant effect on firm's performance of Small-Medium Enterprises, different statistical tests (Demographic Analysis, Descriptive Analysis, Correlation Analysis and Regression Analysis) perform with the help of statistical software (SPSS) to measure the impacts on these variables on the firms performance of Small Medium Enterprises.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.7143965

Introduction

SMEs are defined specifically in the United States according to the sector they serve. For instance, a business can be categorized as a SME if it employs no more than 500 people in the manufacturing sector, whereas a wholesale business can only have 100 employees. Additionally, there are variations amongst an industry's sectors Aksoy (2017). Small and medium-sized firms account for a sizable share of all international businesses worldwide. Although there are certain commonalities, it's vital to keep in mind that each country, as well as the businesses and sectors within it, may define a SME differently (Games, Hidayat, Fhardilha, Fernando, & Sari, 2022). Since changes in surrounding societies have an impact on all facets of corporate culture, according to (Rawlings, Flynn, & Kendal, 2022), managers must be sensitive to them. However, most corporate managers won't be familiar with these changes (Jeong & Chung, 2022). For instance, developing corporate ethics and wellbeing is one of the first tasks given to new company executives. (Sims, 2009) believes that because corporate ethics are defined differently by each business, it is difficult to change this aspect of corporate culture (Andjarwati, Barata, Latif, & Setiono, 2021). Hence, fortifying the imaginative viewpoints and information on SMEs brings significant open doors, as innovation is a key to long haul seriousness and commitments further gains in regards to private area performance and financial improvement (Issau, Acquah, Gnankob, & Hamidu, 2021).

The majority of SMEs must adhere to all of the laws and regulations on the list, which takes into account the standards and operating procedures set forth by the NAICS. It is crucial since many smaller companies can apply for government assistance and contracts as long as they comply with all regulations. Similarly, the concentrate exactly tests the asset based view (ABV) (Zahoor, Khan, Arslan, Khan, & Tarba, 2021). Rather than various past investigations that demonstrate firm's performance as a component of the company's exhibition, this study gives a more clear view upon the connection between the develops of innovation that drive firm's performance. The main goal suggests featuring the significance of firm's innovation and innovation culture on product innovation in SMEs (Kharuddin, Ashhari, & Nassir, 2010). It is understandable why several ethical crises, like those involving Enron and HP, have affected hundreds of American businesses. The reputation of the company is harmed by unethical organizational culture actions, and customers' and workers' loyalty is lost. A few specialists contend that small firms put more in product innovation than they truly do in handle innovation (Koffi, Hongbo, & Zaineldeen, 2021). Hence, this study moves toward just the impact of product innovation on firm's performance.

Organizations need to apply innovation culture in their practices, for example, to permit them to prevail concerning imaginative products and administrations (Astadi, Kristina, Retno, Yahya, & Agni Alam, 2022). It is

inventiveness, strengthening, and changes of authoritative culture that drives innovation. Nonetheless, in spite of the consideration towards the subject of marketing innovation and innovation culture in the writing, past examination didn't adequately dissected the commitment of innovation culture and the effect of advertising innovation on product innovation (Abbas, Khan, & Ahmed Din, 2020). Additionally, the losses can cause the company to suffer financial and economic harm. Managers must create an ethical code that outlines acceptable actions and create a structure of rewards and penalties in order to reform such a culture. Marketing and product innovation techniques are the critical supporters of firm's performance. Seriousness has turned into an imperative component of endurance in the commercial center (Fabrizio et al., 2021). However, some businesses define social or ethical duty as doing any action as long as it is permitted. It is challenging for new managers in such a culture to create an ethical code that aids the company in maintaining their reputation and the goodwill of their staff and clients.

In fact, many executives have failed to act decisively when faced with an ethical or cultural scandal. For instance, Citigroup was severely affected by a cultural crisis, and the leadership had no choice but to maintain corporate silence (Liker, Hoseus, People, & Organizations, 2008). Managers who want to alter the company culture face a significant hurdle from the variety of their workforce. An organization must employ people from various backgrounds even when it has legal and social obligations. This study adds to the current writing by uncovering how the improvement of an exceptional innovation culture and marketing innovation gives SMEs product innovation achievement (Akram, Khan, & Abbas, 2022). It additionally supports that the formation of creative marketing systems and product innovation abilities keep up with unrivaled firm's performance with respect to SMEs. While some organizations are insensitive to the topic of diversity, others have overemphasized it. Since the demographic makeup of the workforce has significantly altered, managers must take this into consideration while establishing or altering organizational culture (Haddad, Williams, Hammoud, & Dwyer, 2019). First and foremost, how much do marketing innovation and product innovation endeavors impact the firm's performance SMEs? Also, how does innovation culture influence on both marketing and product innovation in SMEs? Thirdly, how much do advertising and product innovation interface with one another to influence the firm's performance of SMEs? In this light, the SPSS from recorded Pakistani's SMEs was utilized to test the speculation.

The review starts by talking about the writing and hypothetical foundation of the model, trailed by the depiction of the approach and the inspected tests and measures. The last segments present the outcomes, while featuring a basic survey and potential roads for future exploration.

Theoretical background

Innovation is characterized as an obligatory part of seriousness that compasses the new or further developed product or cycle, another marketing approach, and new hierarchical conduct in strategic policies. It is expected that these innovation types further develop organizations by starting ability and taking on innovative changes (Baharun et al., 2019). Innovation capacity alludes to the aggregated capacity to work on existing innovation and to make new innovation, coming about because of the different inner and outer assets (Khan et al., 2022). Applied to products, processes, hierarchical and marketing innovations, independently or consolidated, it is considered to grow a company's general capacity to start and stay aware of mechanical change (Issau et al., 2021). In light of the important writing, the review breaks down the innovation builds that the exploration proposes, with appearance the develop definitions.

This study tries to inspect the connections between marketing innovation, innovation culture, product innovation, and firm's performance, while zeroing in on SMEs (Sanwal & Ullah, 2021). Accordingly, the reasoning for picking these variables, as far as dissecting the imaginative exercises of SMEs inside Turkey, is supported by the huge number of SMEs from developing business sectors, for example, China, Brazil, India, and Russia, which demonstrates that innovation and advertising performance is basically significant in driving SME performance (Kim & Shim, 2018). To decide reasonable designs required in making the reason to improve a hypothetical model, the review dissects the writing on innovation in SMEs. It likewise applies an asset based view (ABV) to make sense of what SMEs interior assets mean for on performance and energize seriousness (Zahoor et al., 2021). The ABV is a viewpoint that researches the task of the characteristics of those organizations with predominant performance. Moreover, the ABV can be useful in getting a more profound comprehension of such organizations' prosperity contrasted and different organizations (Sarfranz, Shah, Ivascu, & Qureshi, 2022).

The review embraced the connection between free factors and ward variable SME exhibitions, distinguishing the autonomous develops of the procedure as innovation methodology, innovation culture, provider connections (Sun, El Askary, Meo, Zafar, & Hussain, 2022), and mechanical connections, and what these builds mean for SME performance. The current scientist contends that the SMEs' firm's performance depends on the innovation related systems (Bag, Dhamija, Bryde, & Singh, 2022). This view was additionally reached out to relate the imaginative idea of SMEs according to an inventive viewpoint. In such manner, numerous innovations related structures were utilized as expected factors for regulation in the model by various specialists. These incorporate the plan of action, seriousness, culture, and innovation. Similarly, advertising and

innovation support the outcome of many firms and were featured in many marketing and the executives' diaries (Afshar Jahanshahi, Al-Gamrh, & Gharleghi, 2020). To meet this challenge, managers must establish a corporate culture inside their business that would permit the company to cycle people to other foreign locations to learn about the potential and challenges there.

Evidently, this is challenging for the management and expensive for the company. It makes sense that the ability of the firm to foster a culture that equips its employees with the required abilities to integrate into different cultures has been identified by many different types of studies on expatriation as the main obstacle to successful expatriation. (Melitski, Gavin, & Gavin, 2010) provided insight into corporate culture and its adoption in relation to technical innovation. They contend that the adoption of innovative ideas has become crucial to organizational change as firms operate in more uncertain, decentralized, and networked environments. Organizational cultures do, in fact, play a significant role in how businesses choose to use technology and incorporate novel, creative concepts (Kaushik & Singh, 2022). The study's findings also indicated that workplace environments had an impact on workers' readiness to adopt new technologies and innovate. A supportive workplace culture significantly increases the likelihood of innovation and the adoption of original new ideas (Achi, Adeola, & Achi, 2022). Employees who work for companies with structured work are valued for their thoughts, and they are informed about how pertinent issues in the company will be accepted to raise the degree of technology (Melitski et al., 2010). Unfortunately, the majority of businesses lack a culture that encourages people to develop and adopt new technologies. Organizational creative culture changes have recently taken many different turns in terms of technology, work, and employment relations (Hanaysha, Al-Shaikh, Joghee, & Alzoubi, 2022). Technology development and adoption have been linked to outsourcing, downsizing, the rise of contingent labour, and employees who don't stay with one company for their whole career (Scheffknecht, Al-Makhadmeh, Schnell, & Maier, 2011). Therefore, organizational managers have to deal with staff members whose faith in the company has been shaken by internal cultural shifts, and who are therefore likely to be resistant to creative ideas and culture change. It is thought that culture influences innovation-related behaviours in many different ways depending on the organizational context (Incekara, 2022).

Organizational culture may have a direct or indirect impact on how well a company performs in respect to external competition, firm size, technical factors, and management resources. First, a company with strong cultural ethics, like the Toyota Company, could become stagnant, and other factors could improve production performance (Liker et al., 2008). The following actions and behaviours will boost a person's potential for innovation when employees establish morals and standards that place an emphasis on being open to freshly created ideas and invention. The effectiveness of modernization in this organization may be impacted by upbeat group value plans that encourage and direct employees toward innovation. Toyota has built societal norms that promote innovation in order to speed up the adoption of culture by organizational staff (Yeon, Hong, Elangovan, & Divakar, 2022). The level of innovation is influenced by a number of factors, including power distribution, participant judgment, individual and professional development, support, and joint venture. Culture in some organizational groups may imply a readiness to manage and protect employees' schedules. As a result, information and resources are influenced by one another at different organizational levels and across different departments (Rodríguez et al., 2011). It has been noted that participation and honesty in the decision-making process could promote organizational innovation. However, open group cultures that include personnel from different corporate levels are necessary, as seen in the instance of Toyota (Kankisingi & Dhliwayo, 2022). Employees typically assist and support one another in developing ideas and completing tasks thanks to the organizational culture. However, other groups have a tendency to promote solitude by discouraging collaboration and assistance, which lowers the capacity for innovation (Kankisingi & Dhliwayo, 2022). In some communities, culture may forbid members from participating in programmes that would promote capacity expansion through informal education or training. In some workplaces, there are other culturally developed groups that tend to hinder learning and the capacity to come up with novel ideas (Liker et al., 2008). Therefore, an organizational culture must compel its workers to engage in the decision-making process in order to raise the level of commitment and involvement of individuals to create, act freely, and come up with new ideas. In this manner, the current review uses measures in view of advertising innovation, product innovation, and innovation culture (Ahmed & Mwangi, 2022). The calculated system is given by gathering innovation related factors into three unmistakable parts, while deciding how these factors assume a critical part in the outcome of SMEs with regards to showcase performance.

Firm's performance of SME

Taking into account their significance, with regards to monetary innovation, and the significant job they play in numerous economies, the SMEs require more consideration and examination. By the by, it is important to specify that the significance of SMEs is likewise described by the way that all through the world over 95% of endeavors are as SMEs (Al Asheq & Hossain, 2019). Various contrasts between huge firms and SMEs were uncovered in the writing, with regards to adaptability, proprietorship, asset impediments, and dynamic cycles. Because of a portion of these qualities, SMEs have a high level of disappointment. The absence of authority and protection from change and casual arranging processes are the essential explanations behind

SME's disappointment (Hossain & Al Asheq, 2019). Thusly, SMEs are compelled to look for different manners by which to improve and keep an upper hand, like innovation, expanded efficiency, and marketing. Besides, SMEs can apply marketing innovations all the more successfully while attempting to sell imaginative products in nearby or global business sectors. Firms embrace innovation to acquire an upper hand that will at last prompt predominant performance. All things considered, marketing innovation plays a vital part to play in improving products and upgrading firm's performance (Meekaewkunchorn, Szczepańska-Woszczyńska, Muangmee, Kassakorn, & Khalid, 2021). Hence, the point of the current review is to zero in on the connection between firm's innovation and product innovation, concerning unrivaled firm's performance. Firm's performance is characterized as being connected with piece of the pie, deals determiners, income premium of the products, and administrations. Past examinations give proof that the connection among innovation and performance is a positive one (Srhoj, Lapinski, & Walde, 2021). While these investigations featured the effect of innovation on SME performance, not many examinations looked to break down the impact of innovation on SME firm's performance. Thus, the review inspects the connection between various sorts of innovation and SME firm's performance (Ikram et al., 2019).

Cultural Innovation

Since changing the culture necessitates the commitment of both the manager and the workforce, this belief makes it challenging for managers to do so (Pinto & Pinto, 2021). Although managers must take this into account, certain organizational cultures already in place actively reject such initiatives, even going so far as to claim that diversification degrades management quality (Kesavan, 2021). Some organizational cultures have a propensity to undermine the development of novel ideas and fail to inspire workers to take chances. To overcome this, the organization's dominant culture must foster authenticity and lessen anxiety through fostering cooperation and support among team members. This can be promoted by fostering communication and teamwork to support and inspire creative dreams. The workforce will be able to care about innovation for corporate success thanks to such a culture (Ananthasubramaniam, Jurgens, & Romero, 2022). Cultures that encourage support and collaboration tend to improve cross-fertilization of ideas, which affects individual productivity. Toyota promotes participation in order to foster a culture of increased communication and information exchange (Jasovska & Liesch, 2021). Recommendations for how to ensure the development of an acceptable culture any organization's culture has a significant impact on how decisions are made on how to conduct business. Corporate culture is one of the various management models that may be applied by corporation management in expanding, active organizations (Tricarico, Jones, & Daldanise, 2022). However, the management of an organization starts with the development of cultural norms that necessitate the enforcement of the followers' expectations and presumptions. Only by consistently disseminating clear signals about organizational opinions, ethics, and priorities can a suitable culture that fosters innovation and change be implemented. (Ulijn & Weggeman, 2001) assert that there are tactics and activities that are essentially contained in processes that organizational leaders can utilize to develop an appropriate culture.

The management procedures and evaluations that should be routinely taken into consideration when corporate planners and managers clearly express the standards, perspectives, and ideals that should be made known, the proper organizational culture can be developed (Konstantinova, 2022). In actuality, anything that corporate management evaluates ultimately and emphasizes may have a significant impact on corporate culture. When managers are consistent in their own behaviours, this is the most effective method for conveying messages (Romanelli & Ferrara, 2022). The intensity of managerial consistency drives business priorities, ethics, and concepts into every industry, and the company will only uphold such standards. It is important to take advantage of both negative and positive signs to raise employee awareness of what the company's management views as being crucial. The management of the company should continually encourage and discipline personnel as well as pay attention to moral and honourable behaviour. It is hardly sufficient to have an organization's code of conduct (Abdillah, Supriono, & Supriono, 2022).

In addition to sending extremely clear signals that would help the development of a suitable culture, leaders must keep an eye on operational procedures and rules (Faraone, 2022). A company's management can also create a desirable culture by rewarding loyalty and punishing non-cooperation. The management methods must replicate the behavioural models, ideas, attitudes, and views of a corporation's working culture in order for there to be principled behaviours. A suitable culture based on honourable and moral behaviour may be developed in a firm by copying the management's behavior (ERNANI & DEL VALLE). The executive's approach to crisis situations and important events everyone in the organization is aware of disasters when they happen. The organization management's responses are crucial. Organizational culture is revealed through how organizations respond to disasters. During times of crisis, people's deeper cultural values are exposed, which increases the possibility of either changing or preserving the current culture (Ferraris, Giachino, Ciampi, & Couturier, 2021). The executive of the organization should impact such cultures that promote moral behaviour and proper values when a disaster strikes. Therefore, internal organizational crises should be seen as an illustration of adherence to the organization's moral principles (Costantiello, Laureti, & Leogrande, 2021).

Distributing resources, position, and compensation the organizations typically allocate resources in accordance with the beliefs and values of the senior management. Fair resource allocation is crucial for organizations because it increases productivity, boosts employee and customer satisfaction, and, most significantly, increases the organization's worth (Li & Li, 2021). The management's beliefs must therefore be strongly financially backed in order to build an appropriate organizational culture. When resources are being allocated, areas of the organization that show signs of improvement and boost the business's earnings should be given priority. Equitable resource distribution directs an organization's performance toward greater potential areas (Galego, Moulaert, Brans, & Santinha, 2022).

Moral and ethical actions have an equal impact on organizational culture. Evidently, the organization's management should highlight both activities that merit praise and those that merit punishment. Leaders must use performance appraisal systems to assess the efficacy of the workforce in order to improve appropriate organizational culture (Pedeliento, Bettinelli, Andreini, & Bergamaschi, 2018). Employees who are resourceful in applying current abilities or develop new technological know-how should be encouraged through pay raises, support for promotion, or praise. Others will strongly believe that new ideas are bad when an organization responds negatively to innovatively new ideas by mocking the concerned persons. And via adequate orientation, training, and purposeful role modeling, businesses may create the right values. Excommunicating, elevating, and hiring qualified employees are ways to do this (d'Errico et al., 2020).

Theory of the global, cultural environment

Because of the rapid changes in the global business environment, new and innovative company strategies are necessary (Melitski et al., 2010). In addition to changes in laws, diversity, and customer behaviour, the global economy has undergone substantial economic changes, which have a considerable impact on organizational culture. In a risky economic situation, many firms are focusing on developing a culture that can enhance competitive advantages and ultimately the profitability (Milton, 2002). As a result, the emphasis traditionally placed on harmonizing corporate cultures with national cultures has nothing to do with organizational cultures as they are observed today. Small-to-medium-sized businesses (SME) have expanded their operations internationally in pursuit of new commercial prospects (Lima & Castro, 2005). Managers nowadays face a variety of challenges as a result of the evolving global environment. First, as was already mentioned, business cultures vary between nations due to cultural variations. As a company's operations extend abroad, management tasks aimed at preserving and enhancing corporate culture become increasingly complicated. Additionally, it becomes considerably more challenging to coordinate organizational and decision-making concerns (Melitski et al., 2010).

Managers struggle in vain to establish a company culture that strikes a balance between the requirements of international markets and cultural differences with regard to crucial organizational concerns including appraisal, innovation, compensation plans, and promotion rules (Bail, 2014). Second, even managers who are aware of how quickly the world is changing find it difficult to comprehend cultural differences on a worldwide scale. Understanding business conduct in many global environments presents challenges. Globalization makes organizational business culture particularly complex because employee views, preferences, and values vary across nations (Moran, Harris, & Moran, 2010). Once more, when businesses grow globally, the challenges of coordinating activities to fit organizational environments become increasingly challenging. Additionally, a lot of businesses are setting up shop in a certain area to improve efficiency, but doing so also has an impact on the corporate cultures of those businesses. Third, most managers struggle with the global learning that has given foreign businesses a competitive edge in the world market (Bardhan & Weaver, 2011).

The discoveries in the writing show a critical connection among culture and innovation. Innovation is a vital forerunner to rivalry and creates abundance in the business climate. Nonetheless, the utilization of innovation isn't not difficult to embrace without having a culture that urges the association to improve (Pozzo, Filippetti, Paolucci, & Virgili, 2020). Innovation happens when firms inspire their representatives to impart their abilities to the remainder of the association. Thusly, values, convictions, and ways of behaving are shared by hierarchical individuals in a way that forms a innovation culture. This engages organization innovation and the getting of new information that further develops the innovation (Pedeliento et al., 2018). Past investigations examined the essential job of a creative culture on the inventive performance of SMEs. An adaptable creative culture is not entirely settled by low protection from change and profoundly pioneering exercises. Certain analysts featured that making new products includes some trouble for organizations. An inventive culture urges workers to be imaginative and risk-taking and to foster novel thoughts and potential open doors that are fundamental for the product innovation process (Spiro & Crisfield, 2018). In such manner, a lot of scholastic interest in the impacts of an imaginative culture on firm and product performance was shown (C. Wang & Wang, 2020).

An inventive culture can work on the exhibition of the firm and empower the improvement of new products which need imagination, collaboration, open correspondence, and great representative connections. Moreover, SMEs can utilize innovation culture as an essential instrument to work on the presentation and work with the improvement of new products (Kellner, 1997). Innovation culture permits SMEs to recognize new

methodologies for making new channels, while carrying out new techniques for selling an product that has an incentive for clients. Hence, SMEs can acquire an upper hand because of the prevalence of their innovation culture, with regards to further developing productperformance and marketing methodologies, and accomplishing beneficial performance. The writing gives a strong connection regarding the connection between innovation culture and marketing(Senfleben, 2018). Thusly, one can express that SMEs better use advertising innovation in a creative culture climate. A huge connection between creative culture and marketinginnovation is normal; hence:

H1: There is positive and significant relationship between Cultural innovation and firm's performance of small medium enterprises

Marketing Innovation

Developing new Products that consumers will adore while keeping in mind the need to go down a different road that they will want to pursue is known as product innovation(Christofi, Iaia, Marchesani, & Masciarelli, 2021). It is feasible to identify user responses through product innovation, which demonstrates what works and what doesn't. Such a customer's response is what gives any business its competitive edge. Sony uses the brand name Walkman to describe its own line of portable music cassette players. Sony markets their portable audio and video players under the Walkman name, which comes in a variety of models, colours, and features(Tang, Zhang, & Peng, 2021). Sony first released the Walkman in 1979 primarily to revolutionize how people listen to music by enabling them to take their music with them. Additionally, it allows users to listen to music with portable headphones. Due to the brand's present global commercial operations, it has seen significant changes to its appearance, functionality, and features since its foundation. This is the rationale for the report's choice of the Walkman brand (D'Attoma & Ieva, 2020).

Business started with customers' demands and wishes, especially for huge organizations like Apple and IBM, therefore innovation within an organization is essential to its longevity(Abbas, Akram, & Khan, 2022). They observed these societal needs, and in order to capitalize on them and earn a profit, they had to devise a solution that would seize these chances, satisfy consumer demands, and ultimately improve the quality of life for all(Zhang, Tang, & Wu, 2021). And as time went on, these solutions improved and became more valuable. Because of this, entrepreneurs must constantly innovate the new methods without sacrificing quality. If they start to veer off the current trend (due to a lack of innovation skills), it will be difficult for them to catch up, and even worse, they risk losing the game altogether(Sánchez-Gutiérrez, Cabanelas, Lampón, & González-Alvarado, 2018). Productinnovation is huge in the marketing setting since it draws in new clients by promising unrivaled worth and by augmenting firm's sections and product offerings. Many investigations support the positive connection between marketinginnovation and productinnovation. For instance, some demonstrate that marketinginnovation decidedly affects productinnovation. Furthermore, marketinginnovation enables the proposal of less expensive and better quality products (Na, Kang, & Jeong, 2019). Marketinginnovations produce a higher expansion of products, which assists organizations with extending their contributions, while going about as one of the significant wellsprings of upper hand. Thusly, firms ought to utilize new techniques and imaginative marketing thoughts to advance their products that are not notable in the firm's. In similar respect, a significant number of concentrates adroitly guarantee that advertising innovation creates superb productinnovation and productinnovationperformance(Lee & Falahat, 2019).

The marketing capacity and innovationperformance of organizations are firmly related. Innovation is likewise a critical capability of marketing, as firming performance is connected. Subsequently, the astounding revenue with respect to scientists towards the capacity of advertising innovation to increment firm performance is contemplated (Lee & Falahat, 2019). Similarly, marketinginnovation emphatically affects firm performance and a capacity to improve, fortify, and keep up with the company's upper hand as referenced over, the positive connection between marketinginnovation and firm'sperformance is upheld by a tremendous writing, beginning from the possibility that advertising innovation is an essential part of organizations' prosperity (Borysova & Monastyrskyi, 2018). Likewise, SMEs' marketingperformance puts an accentuation on marketinginnovation as the way to seriousness. SMEs embrace marketing inside a cutthroat climate. Taking into account their size, innovation is the most basic component that can be utilized by SMEs to cure any weaknesses. At the point when SMEs keep fostering their ongoing products and administrations, to best address their clients' issues, and spotlight on firm'sperformance, they run into firm's-based innovation(Rebane, 2018). Accordingly, SMEs ought to acquaint advertising innovation techniques with perform better. Subsequently, SMEs ought to can fabricate contrasts in their products, for example, to make separate them from those of their rivals, and present unrivaled client esteem by utilizing advertising innovation. Consequently, the speculation is:

H2: There is positive and significant relationship between marketing innovation and firm's performance of small medium enterprises

Product Innovation

As innovation can be applied in various structures, productinnovation as one of the huge sorts of innovation. There are a few examinations in the writing examining productinnovation(Sinaga, Lumban Gaol, & Ichsan, 2021). Productinnovation is characterized as the turn of events and extremist change in the exhibition

credits of the provided product or administration. The idea overwhelmed most conversations on innovation; since it has the essential significance to fulfill the client's requirements and go into new business sectors (Xie, Huo, & Zou, 2019). The innovation writing proposes that product innovation influences organization performance. With its slogan "You press the button, we do the rest" and the first personal auto camera, Kodak came dangerously close to overtaking Nikon as the leading camera manufacturer in the world in 1964 (Yin, Ming, & Zhang, 2020). Kodak is a clear example of why innovation is such an important factor in the business competition and the consequences that firms may receive if they disrespect their innovative outcome. And the majority of people believe that Kodak produces the greatest cameras in the personal photography sector. People may not be aware that Kodak created the first digital camera in 1975 (Sinaga et al., 2021). Kodak decided to give up on this new product and boost their investment in roll film because they believed that if they invested too much time, money, and effort on this novel and unpredictable product, it might hurt the sales of the classic film. Kodak, a legendary brand in the personal photography sector, had to file for bankruptcy in 2012. Kodak has already lost its competitive advantages in the brutal business battle since they did not understand how important innovation is (Xie et al., 2019).

Meanwhile, their rivals begin to work on this new technology and invest a lot of resources to acquire an edge over them through innovation. While Kodak declares bankruptcy, Apple, the most powerful technology business in the world, has just gained widespread recognition (Awan, Nauman, & Sroufe, 2021). Regardless of SMEs' adaptability and capacity to quickly answer firm's needs, the propensity for product innovation is higher in bigger firms than is the situation in more modest endeavors. Similarly, while dissecting the SMEs related with the improvement of product innovation and the connection between product innovation and firms' exhibition, a review uncovers that the product innovation has a positive relationship with a company's presentation (M. Wang, Li, Li, & Wang, 2021). The creation of new things, redesigning existing items, or manufacturing existing products with the use of new materials or any other components. There are numerous examples of product innovation, including the introduction of new items, improved quality, and greater overall performance. Three distinct categories of innovation—product innovation, cost-cutting innovation, and process innovation—all attempt to advance the company's manufacturing techniques. Distinct types of people have different meanings when it comes to product innovation (Song, Wang, & Zhang, 2020).

Some people, for instance, often consider a product to be the "first of its kind." A measurement of overall customer satisfaction often demonstrates how closely the services offered match the expectations of the customers as well as how far they differ (Ramadani et al., 2019). One of the key factors influencing very long-term consumer behaviour is customer satisfaction. The majority of the business's attention is directed toward managing customer satisfaction as a means of preventing client attrition. The last several years have seen a significant increase in the focus on customer satisfaction across the majority of manufacturing sectors. Customer relationships and returning happy consumers are given more consideration in a fast-paced, competitive industry (Rahmah, Ameen, Isaac, Abu-Elhassan, & Khalifa, 2020). Customer satisfaction is the best method for businesses to set themselves apart from rivals and achieve a competitive edge, but it is also one of the main obstacles in the way of their efforts to raise the bar on quality. The best way to forecast future consumer purchases is through customer satisfaction. Customers who are satisfied are more likely to make further purchases, to suggest the source of their contentment to others, and to be less open to competitors' offerings (Lahindah & Siahaan, 2018). In the past two years, 17.8 million two-wheelers have been sold in this country or around 49,000 units every day. According to a poll by the industry group Society of Indian Automobile Manufacturers and a comparison of statistics from the China Association of Automobile Manufacturers, China came in last with 16.9 million units sold. Third in terms of automobile manufacturing is Indonesia. Exploiting fresh ideas to produce a new product, process, or service is the core definition of innovation.

Additionally, innovation enables managers to better organize their scarce resources among themselves, giving their companies a competitive edge in today's market (Mahmud, Soetanto, & Jack, 2020). However, creating a genuine product or service from those concepts and putting it on the market is what matters most. As a result, firms might make money by developing new ideas. Businesses in the past have been able to thrive with relatively little innovation because, at the time, the quality of the product or service was the main area they should concentrate on (Mostaghel, Oghazi, Patel, Parida, & Hultman, 2019). By focusing only on product quality rather than developing new technologies or production methods, they were also able to generate enough profit by lowering their prices while maintaining or even improving the product's quality. However, huge businesses have started to push themselves to enhance their ability to invent new technology or processes in order to improve the efficiency and effectiveness at the production level in modern society as a result of some issues like globalization and outsourcing (Long & Liao, 2021). Modern organizations want more than simply high quality and competitive pricing; they also need new procedures or management that can cut costs while increasing efficiency. Today, innovation has taken the lead in determining whether a company will succeed over the long term or not. Furthermore, the positive connection between new product improvement and performance is likewise upheld (Al-Abdallah & Al-Salim, 2021). Product innovations are vastly improved fit to organizations

entering a firms, on the grounds that fruitful productinnovation creates benefits, increments portion of the overall industry, and decidedly affects firm'sperformance(Dangelico, 2016). Albeit the writing demonstrates that a more prominent level of productinnovation could increment firm'sperformance,(Kanagal, 2015) results neglected to help this association. In any case, the connection between productinnovation and performance results is upheld(Lyytinen, Yoo, & Boland Jr, 2016). Productinnovation offers better worth than clients, hence, prompts aninnovation in firms' firm'sperformance. Likewise, the speculation is:

H3: There is positive and significant relationship between Product innovation and firm's performance of small medium enterprises

Conceptual Model

Figure: Research Framework

Research Methodology

Quantitative study deals with measurable, quantitative properties of any phenomenon. As data is collected from the population through questionnaire, so study is quantitative in nature. The data is collected from sample of population only at one time, so the research design of this study is cross-sectional in nature. This study is casual because the independent variables are the factor (cause) which is affecting the firm's performance of small medium enterprises (effect). In this study we adopt the questionnaires from the previous studies. Number of five questions (05) for Cultural Innovation, five (05) questions for Marketing Innovation, five (05) questions for Product Innovation and also five (05) questions for performance of SMEs.

Population of study refers to total number of people in the group that sample represent. The selected population of this study are the owners and workers of textile industry and power looms of Multan Region. We collect the data from the textile industry's representatives and workers in Multan region of register textile firms of SMEDA (Small Medium Enterprises Development Authority). The reason for selection of Multan region that is convenience for data collection. The part of population that is under examination to gather the information needed for the study is known as sample. One thousand (291) questionnaires are administered through personally visiting the universities. The sampling technique used in this present study is convenience sampling technique. The unit of analysis of this study is the firm's performance of small medium enterprises through cultural innovation, marketing innovation and product innovation belonging to Multan Region, Pakistan. The nature of data is primary because data has no prior existence. It is generated and collected at same time. The data is collected through five point likert scale questionnaires which determine the impact of cultural innovation, marketing innovation and product innovation on firm's performance of small medium enterprises.

Data Analysis and Results

According to Nunnally (1987), if the value of Cronbach's alpha is greater than 0.7 then the instrument will be reliable. The table depicted that the value of cronbach's alpha of all variables greater than 0.7, so the instrument is reliable.(Leech, Barrett, & Morgan, 2004).The validity of questionnaire is checked by educational experts.

Demographic Analysis

Gender

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Male	284	97.6	97.6	97.6
Female	7	2.4	2.4	100.0
Total	291	100.0	100.0	

Age

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 18-30	58	19.9	19.9	19.9
31-40	117	40.2	40.2	60.1
41-50	58	19.9	19.9	80.1
51-Above	58	19.9	19.9	100.0
Total	291	100.0	100.0	

Qualification

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Primary-Middle	58	19.9	19.9	19.9
Matric-Intermediate	175	60.1	60.1	80.1
Bachelor-Master	57	19.6	19.6	99.7
M.Phil-Ph.D	1	.3	.3	100.0
Total	291	100.0	100.0	

The Data was collected from different people some are male and some are female. The number of male is 284 and female is 07 and total number of people is 291. The cumulative percentage is from female is 100 and from male is 97.6. The age of people range from 18-30 is 58 and the age of people range from 31-40 is 117 and the people range from 41-50 is 59 and the people range from 51-Above is 57 the total number of people is 291. The Primary-Middle people is 58 and Matric-Intermediate people is 175 and Bachelor-Master is 57 and the M.Phil-Ph.D people is 01 the total number of people is 291.

Correlation Analysis

Correlations

		MarketingInnovation	CulturalInnovation	ProductInnovation	FirmPerformance
MarketingInnovation	Pearson Correlation	1	.523**	.410**	.309**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	291	291	291	291
CulturalInnovation	Pearson Correlation	.523**	1	.382**	.270**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	291	291	291	291
ProductInnovation	Pearson Correlation	.410**	.382**	1	.552**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	291	291	291	291
FirmPerformance	Pearson Correlation	.309**	.270**	.552**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	291	291	291	291

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The Correlation shows the relation between the variables. If the value of the Pearson correlation coefficient is between - 0.3 to +0.3 then there exists a weak relationship between the variables. If the value of the Pearson correlation coefficient range is 0.3-0.7 then there exists a moderate relationship. And above 0.7 shows a strong relationship between variables. (Leech, Barrett, & Morgan, 2004). Marketing Innovation Cultural Innovation and Product Innovation have a positive effect on Firm's Performance of Small Medium Enterprises.

Regression Analysis

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
-------	-------------------	-------------------	--------

1	ProductInnovation, CulturalInnovation, MarketingInnovation ^b		. Enter
---	---	--	---------

- a. Dependent Variable: FirmPerformance
- b. All requested variables entered.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.560 ^a	.313	.306	.19548

- a. Predictors: (Constant), ProductInnovation, CulturalInnovation, MarketingInnovation
- b. Dependent Variable: FirmPerformance

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5.002	3	1.667	43.631	.000 ^b
	Residual	10.967	287	.038		
	Total	15.969	290			

- a. Dependent Variable: FirmPerformance
- b. Predictors: (Constant), ProductInnovation, CulturalInnovation, MarketingInnovation

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.205	.444		2.714	.007
	MarketingInnovation	.121	.086	.084	1.413	.159
	CulturalInnovation	.062	.109	.033	.567	.571
	ProductInnovation	.589	.064	.504	9.183	.000

- a. Dependent Variable: FirmPerformance

Residuals Statistics^a

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	4.4966	5.0288	4.8385	.13133	291
Residual	-.33234	.50338	.00000	.19447	291
Std. Predicted Value	-2.603	1.449	.000	1.000	291
Std. Residual	-1.700	2.575	.000	.995	291

- a. Dependent Variable: FirmPerformance

Charts

The regression analysis showed the value of Durbin Watson is in the range. So no problem of serial correlation. The R showed the multiple correlation coefficients. It is the combined correlation of independent

variable and dependent variable. R^2 is the explanatory power of the model. It depicted the explained variation in Dependent variable due to independent variable. It explained the variation for sample and adjusted R square showed the variation for population i.e. Textile industry in Multan Region, Pakistan.

Beta is the slope of relationship. However significant value of the variable (Cultural Innovation, Marketing Innovation and Product Innovation) is less than 0.05, so the relationship between the Cultural Innovation, Marketing Innovation and Product Innovation and firm's performance of small medium enterprises is significant. At the same time, the t value is more than 2, so the hypotheses are accepted.

Hypotheses Result Summary

Hypotheses	Statement of hypotheses	Result
Hypothesis (H1)	There is positive and significant relationship between cultural innovation and firm's performance of small medium enterprises	Accepted
Hypothesis (H2)	There is positive and significant relationship between marketing innovation and firm's performance of small medium enterprises There is positive and significant relationship between product innovation and firm's performance of small medium enterprises	Accepted
Hypothesis (H3)		Accepted

Conclusion and Recommendations

Managerial Implications

The study provides useful insights to SME's managers to design innovation for marketing their product. In addition to this study provides a roadmap and an action plan to the manager to rectify the existing problem of decreased demand by marketing their product on a credible way. As some firms pay their employees to comment about to in favor of SMEs, so this study provides tactics to such SME's that by increasing numbers of review to increase the performance by adopting some innovations in cultural, marketing and in product to increase the performance of the SME's firms.

Theoretical Implications

The findings of this research have made several contributions to the existing literature. Researchers have tested the association of firm's performance with other variables in other sections in the world (Molino, Cortese, & Ghislieri, 2019). The present study has focused on the association of cultural innovation, marketing innovation, product innovation and firm's performance of SMEs in Multan region Pakistan. In previous research, only few researcher have investigated the firms performance and its reaction on innovation.

Research Limitations

The first limitation is that there is resource and time constraint. The limitation of study is that there is no moderation is applied in this study. In addition to above, another sound limitation of study is that it is not taking impact of other factors that influence firms performance such as brand image, purchase decision, and shared geographical location.

Future Research

The first recommendation for the future researcher can replicate the same model in different context. This research has been done in Multan region, Pakistan. So, future research can take other area of the Pakistan in consideration. Secondly, this study is done in the context of only four variables; future research can target other variables (moderator/mediator).

Conclusion

This study highlights that what are the factors that make firm's performance more appealing to people regarding product. People interact with each other and ask different opinions about products and innovation, discuss pros and cons about it, rely onto each other's suggestions and alter their decision according to it. There are different factors that are affecting firm's performance to take advancement in the field to textile industry by using cultural innovation, marketing innovation and product innovation.

Although the cultural innovation affects on the firm's performance therefore for managers and owner of the SMEs should put effort to increase the cultural innovation and similarly marketing and product innovation affects on the firm's performance therefore for also managers and owner of the SMEs should put effort to increase the marketing and product innovation because these factors has significant impact on the firm's performance of small medium enterprises (Abbas et al., 2020). This large discussion on the basis of content and comments generated will attract owner of small medium enterprises and they get more and more benefits by adopting this study to enhance the performance of their firms.

References

- Abbas, A., Akram, M. W., & Khan, I. A. (2022). Nexus between Advertising and Consumer Purchase Decision: Study of Punjab, Pakistan. *Journal of Managerial Sciences*, 16(3), 17-29.
- Abbas, A., Khan, I. A., & Ahmed Din, M. S. (2020). Impact of Advertising on Consumer Purchase Intention: A Study of Southern Punjab.

- Abdillah, Y., Supriono, S., & Supriyono, B. (2022). Change and innovation in the development of Balinese dance in the garb of special interest tourism. *Cogent Social Sciences*, 8(1), 2076962.
- Achi, A., Adeola, O., & Achi, F. C. (2022). CSR and green process innovation as antecedents of micro, small, and medium enterprise performance: Moderating role of perceived environmental volatility. *Journal of Business Research*, 139, 771-781.
- Afshar Jahanshahi, A., Al-Gamrh, B., & Gharlegghi, B. (2020). Sustainable development in Iran post-sanction: Embracing green innovation by small and medium-sized enterprises. *Sustainable Development*, 28(4), 781-790.
- Ahmed, A. Y., & Mwangi, L. W. (2022). Working Capital Management and Financial Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Garissa County, Kenya. *International Journal of Current Aspects in Finance, Banking and Accounting*, 4(1), 56-71.
- Akram, M. W., Khan, I. A., & Abbas, A. (2022). Measuring the Effects of Globalization on Public Purchasing with Mediating Role of Research and Development: Empirical Evidence from Pakistan. *Journal of Managerial Sciences*, 16(1), 109-130.
- Aksoy, H. (2017). How do innovation culture, marketing innovation and product innovation affect the market performance of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). *Technology in Society*, 51(4), 133-141.
- Al-Abdallah, G. M., & Al-Salim, M. I. (2021). Green product innovation and competitive advantage: an empirical study of chemical industrial plants in Jordanian qualified industrial zones. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*.
- Al Asheq, A., & Hossain, M. U. (2019). SME performance: Impact of market, customer and brand orientation. *Academy of marketing studies journal*, 23(1), 1-9.
- Ananthasubramaniam, A., Jurgens, D., & Romero, D. M. (2022). Networks and Identity Drive Geographic Properties of the Diffusion of Linguistic Innovation. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2202.04842*.
- Andjarwati, T., Barata, F. A., Latif, I. N., & Setiono, B. A. (2021). The Effect of Entrepreneurial Characteristics and Business Capital and Innovation on Marketing Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). *International Journal of eBusiness and eGovernment Studies*, 13(1), 142-158.
- Astadi, P., Kristina, S., Retno, S., Yahya, P., & Agni Alam, A. (2022). The long path to achieving green economy performance for micro small medium enterprise. *Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 11(1), 1-19.
- Awan, U., Nauman, S., & Sroufe, R. (2021). Exploring the effect of buyer engagement on green product innovation: Empirical evidence from manufacturers. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 30(1), 463-477.
- Bag, S., Dhamija, P., Bryde, D. J., & Singh, R. K. (2022). Effect of eco-innovation on green supply chain management, circular economy capability, and performance of small and medium enterprises. *Journal of Business Research*, 141, 60-72.
- Baharun, R., Mi, T. J., Streimikiene, D., Mardani, A., Shakeel, J., & Nitsenko, V. S. (2019). Innovation in healthcare performance among private brand's healthcare services in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs).
- Bail, C. A. (2014). The cultural environment: Measuring culture with big data. *Theory and Society*, 43(3), 465-482.
- Bardhan, N., & Weaver, C. K. (2011). Introduction: Public relations in global cultural contexts *Public relations in global cultural contexts* (pp. 1-28): Routledge.
- Borysova, T., & Monastyrskiy, G. (2018). Marketing innovation activity of urban public transport: results of the empirical study. *Маркетинг і менеджмент інновацій*(3), 229-240.
- Christofi, M., Iaia, L., Marchesani, F., & Masciarelli, F. (2021). Marketing innovation and internationalization in smart city development: a systematic review, framework and research agenda. *International Marketing Review*.
- Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The Innovation-Friendly Environment in Europe. *Available at SSRN 3933553*.
- D'Attoma, I., & Ieva, M. (2020). Determinants of technological innovation success and failure: Does marketing innovation matter? *Industrial Marketing Management*, 91, 64-81.
- d'Errico, F., Martí, A. P., Shipton, C., Le Vraux, E., Ndiema, E., Goldstein, S., . . . Boivin, N. (2020). Trajectories of cultural innovation from the Middle to Later Stone Age in Eastern Africa: Personal ornaments, bone artifacts, and ocher from Panga ya Saidi, Kenya. *Journal of Human Evolution*, 141, 102737.
- Dangelico, R. M. (2016). Green product innovation: Where we are and where we are going. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 25(8), 560-576.
- ERNANI, A. M., & DEL VALLE, R. S. S. Innovation and Cultural Heritage. *European Cities in the Process of Constructing and Transmitting European Cultural Heritage*, 173.

- Fabrizio, C. M., Kaczam, F., de Moura, G. L., da Silva, L. S. C. V., da Silva, W. V., & da Veiga, C. P. (2021). Competitive advantage and dynamic capability in small and medium-sized enterprises: a systematic literature review and future research directions. *Review of Managerial Science*, 1-32.
- Faraone, C. (2022). Territorial Challenges for Cultural and Creative Industries' Contribution to Sustainable Innovation: Evidence from the Interreg Ita-Slo Project DIVA. *Sustainability*, 14(18), 11271.
- Ferraris, A., Giachino, C., Ciampi, F., & Couturier, J. (2021). R&D internationalization in medium-sized firms: The moderating role of knowledge management in enhancing innovation performances. *Journal of Business Research*, 128, 711-718.
- Galego, D., Moulaert, F., Brans, M., & Santinha, G. (2022). Social innovation & governance: a scoping review. *Innovation: The European Journal of Social Science Research*, 35(2), 265-290.
- Games, D., Hidayat, T., Fhardilha, J., Fernando, Y., & Sari, D. K. (2022). The Impact of Trust, Knowledge Sharing, and Affective Commitment on SME Innovation Performance. *Journal of Governance and Integrity*, 5(2), 267-274.
- Haddad, M. I., Williams, I. A., Hammoud, M. S., & Dwyer, R. J. (2019). Strategies for implementing innovation in small and medium-sized enterprises. *World journal of entrepreneurship, management and sustainable development*.
- Hanaysha, J. R., Al-Shaikh, M. E., Joghee, S., & Alzoubi, H. M. (2022). Impact of innovation capabilities on business sustainability in small and medium enterprises. *FIIB Business Review*, 11(1), 67-78.
- Hossain, M. U., & Al Asheq, A. (2019). The role of entrepreneurial orientation to SME performance in Bangladesh. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 23(1), 1-6.
- Ikram, M., Sroufe, R., Mohsin, M., Solangi, Y. A., Shah, S. Z. A., & Shahzad, F. (2019). Does CSR influence firm performance? A longitudinal study of SME sectors of Pakistan. *Journal of Global Responsibility*.
- İncekara, M. (2022). Determinants of process reengineering and waste management as resource efficiency practices and their impact on production cost performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in the manufacturing sector. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 356, 131712.
- Issau, K., Acquah, I. S. K., Gnankob, R. I., & Hamidu, Z. (2021). Innovation orientation and performance of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMES) in Ghana: evidence from manufacturing sector. *Innovation & Management Review*(ahead-of-print).
- Jasovska, P., & Liesch, P. (2021). Entrepreneurial market-making across borders: The case of cultural and technological innovation *Contemporary Entrepreneurship Issues in International Business* (pp. 27-58): World Scientific.
- Jeong, S. W., & Chung, J.-E. (2022). Enhancing competitive advantage and financial performance of consumer-goods SMEs in export markets: how do social capital and marketing innovation matter? *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*.
- Kanagal, N. B. (2015). Innovation and product innovation in marketing strategy.
- Kankisingi, G. M., & Dhliwayo, S. (2022). Rewards and Innovation Performance in Manufacturing Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). *Sustainability*, 14(3), 1737.
- Kaushik, A., & Singh, D. (2022). Performance evaluation of advanced manufacturing technologies in small and medium enterprises located in Northern India. *International Journal of Business Excellence*, 26(3), 281-298.
- Kellner, D. (1997). Critical theory and cultural studies: The missed articulation. *Cultural methodologies*, 12-41.
- Kesavan, P. (2021). Findings: Social Innovation, Architectural Innovation, and Cultural Innovation *Enablers of Organisational Learning, Knowledge Management, and Innovation* (pp. 135-203): Springer.
- Khan, R. U., Mehmood, A., Ahmed, M., Mustafa, M. J., Alshamsi, M. K., Iqbal, Q., & Salamzadeh, Y. (2022). Impact of network structure on sustainable competitive performance among Pakistani small and medium enterprises: Does government financial support matter? *Journal of Global Entrepreneurship Research*, 1-13.
- Kharuddin, S., Ashhari, Z. M., & Nassir, A. M. (2010). Information system and firms' performance: The case of Malaysian small medium enterprises. *International business research*, 3(4), 28.
- Kim, N., & Shim, C. (2018). Social capital, knowledge sharing and innovation of small-and medium-sized enterprises in a tourism cluster. *International journal of contemporary hospitality management*.
- Koffi, A. L., Hongbo, L., & Zaineldeen, S. (2021). Examining the Impact of Innovation types on Ivorian Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) Performance and Competitiveness.
- Konstantinova, Y. (2022). Cultural tourism development in the town of Byala-opportunities for innovation. *Access to science, business, innovation in digital economy*, 67-80.
- Lahindah, L., & Siahaan, R. A. (2018). The influence of product innovation and service quality to buying decision and the impact to repeat buying at Progo Road Bandung. *The Asian Journal of Technology Management*, 11(2), 118-124.

- Lee, Y. Y., & Falahat, M. (2019). The impact of digitalization and resources on gaining competitive advantage in international markets: Mediating role of marketing, innovation and learning capabilities. *Technology Innovation Management Review*, 9(11).
- Leech, N., Barrett, K., & Morgan, G. (2004). *SPSS for introductory statistics: Use and interpretation*: Psychology Press.
- Li, X., & Li, Z. (2021). *Design Innovation of Intangible Cultural Heritage: Challenges on the Basis of Mobile Phone Culture*. Paper presented at the International Conference on Human-Computer Interaction.
- Liker, J. K., Hoseus, M., People, C. f. Q., & Organizations. (2008). *Toyota culture*: McGraw-Hill Publishing New York.
- Lima, M. L., & Castro, P. (2005). Cultural theory meets the community: Worldviews and local issues. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 25(1), 23-35.
- Long, S., & Liao, Z. (2021). Are fiscal policy incentives effective in stimulating firms' eco-product innovation? The moderating role of dynamic capabilities. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 30(7), 3095-3104.
- Lyytinen, K., Yoo, Y., & Boland Jr, R. J. (2016). Digital product innovation within four classes of innovation networks. *Information Systems Journal*, 26(1), 47-75.
- Mahmud, M., Soetanto, D., & Jack, S. (2020). Environmental management and product innovation: the moderating role of the dynamic capability of small manufacturing firms. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 264, 121633.
- Meekaewkunchorn, N., Szczepańska-Woszczyna, K., Muangmee, C., Kassakorn, N., & Khalid, B. (2021). Entrepreneurial orientation and SME performance: The mediating role of learning orientation. *Economics & Sociology*, 14(2), 294-312.
- Melitski, J., Gavin, D., & Gavin, J. (2010). Technology adoption and organizational culture in public organizations. *International Journal of Organization Theory & Behavior*.
- Milton, K. (2002). *Environmentalism and cultural theory: exploring the role of anthropology in environmental discourse*: Routledge.
- Molino, M., Cortese, C. G., & Ghislieri, C. (2019). Unsustainable working conditions: The association of destructive leadership, use of technology, and workload with workaholism and exhaustion. *Sustainability*, 11(2), 446.
- Moran, R. T., Harris, P. R., & Moran, S. (2010). *Managing cultural differences*: Routledge.
- Mostaghel, R., Oghazi, P., Patel, P. C., Parida, V., & Hultman, M. (2019). Marketing and supply chain coordination and intelligence quality: A product innovation performance perspective. *Journal of Business Research*, 101, 597-606.
- Na, Y. K., Kang, S., & Jeong, H. Y. (2019). The effect of market orientation on performance of sharing economy business: Focusing on marketing innovation and sustainable competitive advantage. *Sustainability*, 11(3), 729.
- Pedeliento, G., Bettinelli, C., Andreini, D., & Bergamaschi, M. (2018). Consumer entrepreneurship and cultural innovation: The case of GinO12. *Journal of Business Research*, 92, 431-442.
- Pinto, A. G., & Pinto, P. R. (2021). Searching for sustainable alternatives and socio-cultural innovation through participatory art and design *Tradition and Innovation* (pp. 337-342): CRC Press.
- Pozzo, R., Filippetti, A., Paolucci, M., & Virgili, V. (2020). What does cultural innovation stand for? Dimensions, processes, outcomes of a new innovation category. *Science and Public Policy*, 47(3), 425-433.
- Rahmah, M., Ameen, A., Isaac, O., Abu-Elhassan, A., & Khalifa, G. (2020). Effect of organizational innovation (product innovation, process innovation, and administrative innovation) on organizational learning. *Test Engineering and Management*, 82, 12101-12113.
- Ramadani, V., Hisrich, R. D., Abazi-Alili, H., Dana, L.-P., Panthi, L., & Abazi-Bexheti, L. (2019). Product innovation and firm performance in transition economies: A multi-stage estimation approach. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 140, 271-280.
- Rawlings, B. S., Flynn, E. G., & Kendal, R. L. (2022). Personality predicts innovation and social learning in children: Implications for cultural evolution. *Developmental science*, 25(1), e13153.
- Rebane, T. (2018). Complementarities in performance between product innovation, marketing innovation and cooperation with clients. *The University of Tartu FEBA*.
- Rodríguez, N., Alonso, M., Abanades, J. C., Charitos, A., Hawthorne, C., Scheffknecht, G., . . . Anthony, E. J. (2011). Comparison of experimental results from three dual fluidized bed test facilities capturing CO₂ with CaO. *Energy Procedia*, 4, 393-401.
- Romanelli, M., & Ferrara, M. (2022). Museums Driving Innovation by Technology, People and Organisation *Do Machines Dream of Electric Workers?* (pp. 119-135): Springer.
- Sánchez-Gutiérrez, J., Cabanelas, P., Lampón, J. F., & González-Alvarado, T. E. (2018). The impact on competitiveness of customer value creation through relationship capabilities and marketing innovation. *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing*.

- Sanwal, A. K., & Ullah, H. (2021). Impact of Advertising on Brand Image: Evidence from Southern Punjab Pakistan. *Journal of International Business and Management Studies*, 2(1).
- Sarfraz, M., Shah, S. G. M., Ivascu, L., & Qureshi, M. A. A. (2022). Explicating the impact of hierarchical CEO succession on small-medium enterprises' performance and cash holdings. *International Journal of Finance & Economics*, 27(2), 2600-2614.
- Scheffknecht, G., Al-Makhadmeh, L., Schnell, U., & Maier, J. (2011). Oxy-fuel coal combustion—A review of the current state-of-the-art. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*, 5, S16-S35.
- Senftleben, M. (2018). A Clash of Culture and Commerce—Non-Traditional Marks and the Impediment of Cyclic Cultural Innovation.
- Sims, R. (2009). Food, place and authenticity: local food and the sustainable tourism experience. *Journal of sustainable tourism*, 17(3), 321-336.
- Sinaga, S., Lumban Gaol, J., & Ichsan, R. N. (2021). The effect of product innovation on consumer interest in the purchase of bottled tes product at PT. Sinar sosro medan. *Budapest International Research and Critics Institute (BIRCI-Journal): Humanities and Social Sciences*, 4(1).
- Song, M., Wang, S., & Zhang, H. (2020). Could environmental regulation and R&D tax incentives affect green product innovation? *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 258, 120849.
- Spiro, J., & Crisfield, E. (2018). Linguistic and Cultural Innovation in Schools. *Cham, Switzerland: Palgrave MacMillan*.
- Srroj, S., Lapinski, M., & Walde, J. (2021). Impact evaluation of business development grants on SME performance. *Small Business Economics*, 57(3), 1285-1301.
- Sun, X., El Askary, A., Meo, M. S., Zafar, N. u. A., & Hussain, B. (2022). Green transformational leadership and environmental performance in small and medium enterprises. *Economic Research-Ekonomiska Istraživanja*, 1-19.
- Tang, T. Y., Zhang, S. K., & Peng, J. (2021). The value of marketing innovation: Market-driven versus market-driving. *Journal of Business Research*, 126, 88-98.
- Tricarico, L., Jones, Z. M., & Daldanise, G. (2022). Platform Spaces: When culture and the arts intersect territorial development and social innovation, a view from the Italian context. *Journal of Urban Affairs*, 44(4-5), 545-566.
- Ulijn, J. M., & Weggeman, M. (2001). Towards an innovation culture: what are it's national, corporate, marketing and engineering aspects, some experimental evidence *Handbook of organizational culture and climate* (pp. 487-517): Wiley.
- Wang, C., & Wang, Y. (2020). Opportunities for digital culture and innovation under cultural construction in the big data era--take digital cultural innovation in jiangxi universities as an example. *International Journal of Social Science and Education Research*, 2(11), 38-43.
- Wang, M., Li, Y., Li, J., & Wang, Z. (2021). Green process innovation, green product innovation and its economic performance improvement paths: A survey and structural model. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 297, 113282.
- Xie, X., Huo, J., & Zou, H. (2019). Green process innovation, green product innovation, and corporate financial performance: A content analysis method. *Journal of Business Research*, 101, 697-706.
- Yeon, G., Hong, P. C., Elangovan, N., & Divakar, G. (2022). Implementing strategic responses in the COVID-19 market crisis: a study of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in India. *Journal of Indian Business Research*.
- Yin, D., Ming, X., & Zhang, X. (2020). Sustainable and smart product innovation ecosystem: An integrative status review and future perspectives. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 274, 123005.
- Zahoor, N., Khan, Z., Arslan, A., Khan, H., & Tarba, S. Y. (2021). International open innovation and international market success: an empirical study of emerging market small and medium-sized enterprises. *International Marketing Review*.
- Zhang, S. K., Tang, T. Y., & Wu, F. (2021). The ambidextrous patterns for managing technological and marketing innovation. *Industrial marketing management*, 92, 34-44.

Author Information

Irfan Ahmad Khan

Ph.D Scholar, Institute of Commerce and Management, Shah Abdul Latif University, Khairpur

Amir Hussain Shar

Dean, Faculty of Management Sciences, Shah Abdul Latif University, Khairpur
 Prof. Institute of Commerce and Management, Shah Abdul Latif University, Khairpur

Mumtaz Ali Junejo

Ex-Dean, Faculty of Management Sciences, Shah Abdul Latif University, Khairpur

Prof. Institute of Commerce and Management, Shah
Abdul Latif University, Khairpur
